

Determination of alkylating agents in pure form and in pharmaceutical preparations with *N*-bromosuccinimide reagent

I. C. Shukla*, P. K. Dwivedi and Poonam Jaiswal

Department of Chemistry, University of Allahabad, Allahabad-211 002, Uttar Pradesh, India

E-mail : ponamjail@rediffmail.com

Manuscript received 8 October 2004, revised 7 March 2005, accepted 19 May 2005

Abstract : A simple and convenient method has been developed for the determination of some alkylating agents e.g. cyclophosphamide, chlorambucil, melphalan and busulphan in pure form and in their pharmaceutical preparation with the use of *N*-bromosuccinimide reagent. The value of % error, SD and CV prove the method to be precise and reproducible.

Keywords : Alkylating agent, pharmaceutical preparations.

The term alkylating agent is applied to compound which in sense "alkylate" the substance with which they react by joining it through a covalent bond. Any antitumor agent whose activity is explainable by such a mechanism is called alkylating agents. According to Ludlam and Tong alkylating agents are nitrogen mustards alkyl sulfonates, ethylenimines, nitrosoureas, triazenes etc. Alkylating agents are used in chemotherapy of neoplastic diseases. Biological evaluation correlate that derivative of melphalan² with alkylating moiety prevent carcinogenesis for multiple myeloma. A series of amidine analogues of chlorambucil are potent against the growth of human breast cancer MCF-7 cell³. Because of their clinical antineoplastic activity, their estimations have widely been studied⁴⁻¹¹. In the present paper we describe a simple and convenient method for the determination of alkylating agents with *N*-bromosuccinimide reagent.

Results and discussion

Taking cyclophosphamide as the test sample, the reaction conditions were established after studying the effect of variables such as reaction time, reagent concentration (*N*-bromosuccinimide), reaction temperature, volume of reagent and volume of glacial acetic acid. Variation in reaction time was found to influence the speed of the reaction to an appreciable extent. The determination of cyclophosphamide, chlorambucil, melphalan and busulphan required 5 min to complete the reaction. At a lesser reaction time (1-4 min) the reaction is not complete, therefore low recovery was obtained. A much more reaction time (6-30 min) also does not improve the % recovery. The effect of concentration of reagent was also

established. It was found that the present concentration (0.02 *N*) of *N*-bromosuccinimide was suitable for accurate results. A lower (0.01-0.015 *N*) or higher (0.025-0.5 *N*) concentration tends to give inaccurate results. The reactivity of the reagent was slow without the presence of ionising medium. Since mineral acids like H₂SO₄ and HNO₃ may decompose the reagent, glacial acetic acid was tried. While studying the effect of variation in volume of glacial acetic acid it was found that 5 ml glacial acetic acid was suitable for quantitative results. The best recovery of the sample was obtained at room temperature (25-27 °C). Higher temperature (30-60 °C) gave inaccurate results because of decomposition of the reagent. At lower temperature (5 °C) the reactivity was very slow. The method is applicable for 1-10 mg sample size but for convenience, results are given for 1 and 5 mg only (Table 1). For calculating recovery of the sample the determination of stoichiometry was essential. It was established by allowing the reaction to proceed for different intervals of time (1-10 min) with excess of the reagent and calculating the recovery. At a reaction time of five minutes the recovery becomes constant (cyclophosphamide, busulphan, melphalan and chlorambucil). For all the compounds the stoichiometry was found to be two. The value of standard deviation (SD), coefficient of variation (CV) and percentage error indicate that the proposed method is accurate and reproducible. It can easily be adopted in an ordinary laboratory. As stated above, cyclophosphamide; [*N,N*-bis(2-chloroethylamino)tetrahydro-2*H*-1,3,2-oxozaphosphorine-2-oxide], chlorambucil; 4-[bis(2-chloroethyl)amino]benzene butyric acid; melphalan; L-PAM; 4-[bis(2-chloroethyl)amino]-L-phenylalanine; L-phe-

Note

Table 1. Determination of some alkylating agents in the pure form and their pharmaceutical preparations with 0.02 *N*-bromosuccinimide reagent in acidic medium

Sl. no.	Sample	Aliquots taken (ml)	Amount present (mg)	Amount obtained by calculation ^a (mg)	Error (%)	SD (mg)	CV (%)
1.	Cyclophosphamide pure	1.0	0.99	0.984	-0.60	0.0099	1.0061
		5.0	4.99	4.920	-1.40	0.0012	0.0243
a.	Cyclophosphamide tablets	1.0	0.99	0.984	-0.60	0.0099	1.0061
		5.0	4.99	4.920	-1.40	0.0012	0.0243
b.	Cyclophosphamide injection	1.0	0.99	0.988	-0.20	0.0088	0.8906
		5.0	4.99	4.940	-1.00	0.0066	0.1336
c.	Cycloxan tablets	1.0	0.99	0.986	-0.40	0.0096	0.9736
		5.0	4.99	4.930	-1.20	0.0091	0.1845
d.	Endo-Astra tablets	1.0	0.99	0.984	-0.60	0.0093	0.9451
		5.0	4.99	4.920	-1.40	0.0012	0.0243
2.	Chlorambucil pure	1.0	0.99	0.992	-0.20	0.0033	0.3326
		5.0	4.99	4.960	-0.60	0.0053	0.1068
a.	Leukeram injection	1.0	0.99	0.996	-0.60	0.0011	0.1104
		5.0	4.99	4.980	-0.20	0.0088	0.1767
3.	Melphalan pure	1.0	0.99	0.984	-0.60	0.0099	1.0061
		5.0	4.99	4.920	-1.40	0.0012	0.0243
a.	Alkeran injection	1.0	0.99	0.988	-0.20	0.0088	0.8906
		5.0	4.99	4.950	-0.80	0.0093	0.1878
4.	Busulphan pure	1.0	0.99	0.986	-0.40	0.0095	0.9634
		5.0	4.99	4.930	-1.20	0.0091	0.1845
a.	Myleram tablets	1.0	0.99	0.986	-0.40	0.0092	0.9331
		5.0	4.99	4.930	-1.20	0.0093	0.1886
b.	Myram tablets	1.0	0.99	0.984	-0.60	0.0097	0.9857
		5.0	4.99	4.920	-1.40	0.0013	0.0264

^aAverage of nine determination.

For all the compounds the reaction time is 5 min and the molecularity is 2 only.

nylanaline mustard L-isomer consume only 2 moles of *N*-bromosuccinimide. Busulphan (bis substituted methane sulfonic acid ester) in which the length of a bridge of methylene is two ($n = 2$) also consumed 2 moles of *N*-bromosuccinimide. On the basis of the structure of the compounds and the molecularity of the reagent, a possible

course of reaction may be proposed for different compounds. Cyclophosphamide consumes two moles of the

reagent and gets brominated at active positions giving rise to dibromo derivative.

Similarly chlorambucil gives corresponding bromi-

nated product by consuming two moles of the reagent.

Melphalan has activated benzene ring at ortho position to substituted amino group. Therefore these position are brominated and give dibromo derivative.

In case of busulphan following reaction may be proposed.

Experimental

Solution preparation : The sample solution (1 mg/ml) of alkylating agents like cyclophosphamide, chorambucil, melphalan and busulphan were prepared by dissolving accurately weighed amount of the sample (100 mg) in double distilled water in 100 ml volumetric flask. Compounds used in the study were obtained by Merck and Fluka. In case of pharmaceutical preparations, accurately weighed tablets were crushed and dissolved in distilled water to give a strength of 1 mg/ml. Similarly the injection of pure sample were also dissolved in distilled water (1 mg/ml). There was no indication of any insolubility in pharmaceutical preparations.

A fresh solution of 0.02 N *N*-bromosuccinimide (May and Baker) was prepared in small amount of warm double distilled water and then transferred to volumetric flask (100 ml) and made up to the volume with cold distilled water. The solution was standardised iodometrically. A stock solution of 0.02 N sodium thiosulphate (B.D.H.) in distilled water was prepared and standardised by titrating against primary standard (0.02 N) copper sulphate solution iodometrically. A 0.02 N copper sulphate (G.R.) solution was prepared in distilled water containing small amount of dil. sulphuric acid to prevent hydrolysis of copper sulphate. A 10% w/v aqueous solution of KI (Baker

analysed reagent) and 1% w/v aqueous starch solution (indicator) was also prepared. Glacial acetic acid (Merck) was used without any dilution.

Procedure : An aliquot containing 1–5 mg of the sample was taken in 100 ml stoppered iodine flask followed by the addition of 5 ml 0.02 N *N*-bromosuccinimide solution and 5 ml glacial acetic acid. The reaction mixture was shaken thoroughly and allowed to react at 25–30 °C for 5 min. After the reaction was over 5 ml KI solution was added to it, contents shaken thoroughly and allowed to stand for a minute. The liberated iodine was titrated with standardised 0.02 N sodium thiosulphate solution to starch end point. A blank experiment was also performed under identical conditions using all the reagents except the sample.

Calculation : The amount of the sample was calculated by the following expression.

$$\text{mg of the sample} = \frac{MN(B - S)}{n}$$

where, *M* = molecular weight of the sample, *N* = normality of sodium thiosulphate solution, *B* = volume of sodium thiosulphate solution for blank, *S* = volume of sodium thiosulphate solution for sample, *n* = number of moles of *N*-bromosuccinimide consumed per mole of the sample. The calculation of standard deviation and coefficient of variations were also done on the basis of the error obtained.

References

1. D. B. Ludlum and W. P. Tong, "DNA Modification by Nitrosoureas, Chemical Nature and Cellular Repair", *Cancer Chemotherapy*, 1985, Vol. II, Martinus Nijhoff, Boston 141.
2. K. Bielawska, A. Bielawska and S. Wolczynski, *S. Biol. Pharm. Bull.*, 2002, 25, 916.
3. A. Bielawska, A. Bielawska, A. Muszynska and Tomasz Anchim, *Joint Meeting on Medicinal Chemistry*, 2003, P120, 154.
4. S. M. Somani and San Diego, "Chemical Warfare Agents", 1992, Ch. 2, 13.
5. E. G. Levine and Bloomfield, *Semin. Oncol.*, 1992, 19, 47.
6. S. T. Garcia, A. Mcquillan and L. Panasci, *Biochem. Pharmacol.*, 1988, 37, 3189.
7. D. S. Alberts, S. Y. Chang, H. S. G. Chen, J. E. Moon, T. L. Evans, R. L. Furner, K. Himmelstein and J. F. Gross, *Clin. Pharmacol. Ther.*, 1979b, 26, 73.
8. D. E. Fisher, "Apoptosis in Cancer Therapy : Crossing the Threshold Cell", 1994, 78, 539.
9. W. P. Long and D. B. Ludlum, *Biochem. Biophys. Acta*, 1980, 608, 174.
10. F. Gonzaga, E. Perez, I. Lattes and A. Lattes, *New. J. Chem.*, 2001, 25, 151.
11. K. Bielawski, A. Bielawska and S. Wolczynsi, *Joint Meeting in Medicinal Chemistry*, 2003. P121, 155.